

OXIDATIVE STRESS IN BLACK-NECKED PHEASANTS WITH SIGNS OF CANNIBALISM – THE USE OF TRYPTOPHAN AND SILYMARIN AS ANTIOXIDANTS

Slavko Nikolov*, Dian Kanakov, Veselin Ivanov, Galina Nikolova,
Yanka Karamalakova

Trakia University, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Stara Zagora, Bulgaria
E-mail: slavko92@outlook.com

ABSTRACT

The oxidative stress indicators were studied – Malondialdehyde, Protein carbonyl content, Superoxide dismutase and Catalase in Black-necked pheasants. Blood samples were taken from pheasants, divided into 4 groups (n=12): I group (negative control) – clinically healthy; II group – treated with tryptophan; III group – treated with silymarin; IV group (positive control) – pheasants with signs of cannibalism. Lipid peroxidation were expressed in MDA and the protein oxidation with increased PCC. This was found in the positive control with value for MDA (5.16±0.39) and PCC (7.70±0.45), respectively the negative control (2.35±0.19) and (1.46±0.25). The tendency for SOD was opposite with very high activity in the negative control (2.99±0.10), and in the positive control was (1.64±0.20). Compensatory, the activity of CAT levels in the negative control (1.33±0.24) was higher in comparison to the positive control (6.65±0.73). The silymarin had pronounced anti-oxidant effect on each of the observed indicators, while the effects of tryptophan were in lower rate.

Key words: Black-necked pheasants, Malondialdehyde, Protein carbonyl content, Superoxide dismutase, Catalase.

Introduction

The most common species of game birds in Bulgaria and worldwide are black – necked pheasants (*Phasianus colchicus colchicus*). When raised in hunting farms there are often mistakes in the feeding – proteins, minerals, fibers (Kuzniacka & Adamski, 2010; Kokoszynski *et al.*, 2011), disruption of the abiotic factors – light, temperature, air, sound (Gilani *et al.*, 2013; Daigle, 2017) or the breeding parameters – density, size of the group and the barrage (Kjaer & Johnsen, 2000). More examples of disturbances in the individual characteristics in every individual are – social, sex, age, nervous, genetics and other factors (Appleby *et al.*, 2004; Zapletal *et al.*, 2011). These groups of factors lead to the development of damaging behavior in birds. A main issue causing serious economic losses in the breeding of game birds in captivity and damaging their welfare is injurious pecking. Injurious pecking includes pecking of the feathers which damages the feathering of the birds while tissue pecking (cannibalism) can directly lead to mortality in a big number of individuals (Sedlacova *et al.*, 2004; Van Krimpen *et al.*, 2005).

The use of tryptophan in hens that manifest feather pecking and cannibalism improves and lowers the manifestation of injurious pecking amongst them (Birkel *et al.*, 2017). The effects of administering the amino acid in game birds and pheasants haven't been observed yet. The administration of milk thistle (silymarin) extract in chicken broilers (Stoef *et al.*, 2021; Denev *et al.*, 2020) and quails (Pavlova *et al.*, 2018; Lukanov *et al.*, 2018) is significant. But the hepatoprotective and antioxidative effect of silymarin in pheasants is not known. The objective of the study is to test the effects of tryptophan and silymarin administration in black-necked pheasants with signs of cannibalism.

Materials and methods

The black necked pheasants were divided into 4 groups, aged 52–54 weeks, equally distributed by gender, 12 in number in each group as it follows: I group (negative control) clinically healthy pheasants fed on standard forage. II experimental group – in which pheasants with signs of cannibalism received forage with 21 g/kg tryptophan. L – Tryptophan shipped by ST Island 0767-012A/ PO № 20200219 – VIAND / Ever Lunar 1316-022W/ BBD: 12.02.2023 (PT. Cheil Jedang Indonesia, Indonesia). III experimental group in which pheasants with signs of cannibalism received forage with 10g/kg silymarin (78% *Extr. Silybum marianum*). The standardized Silymarin milk thistle extract used was a light yellow powder obtained from Wuxi Gorunjie Technology Co Ltd, Jiangsu, China. The sample was listed as INM-7035. IV group pheasants (positive control) with signs of cannibalism. The study was conducted in a 30-day period. The test substances together with the forage were added once daily in the morning at 9:00. The pheasants were reared in an aviary of size 6m x 4m x 2m. Blood samples of 1 ml were obtained from every bird and transferred into heparin tubes. Samples were processed within 1-3 hours after collection at 6° C. The centrifugation was conducted at 3000 revolution per minute with a non-refrigerated centrifuge BS-120 (Mindray, China). To test the levels of lipid peroxidation in plasma – malondialdehyde (MDA) we used a spectrophotometric method with spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, England). Trichloroacetic and thiobarbituric acid (TBA) were purchase from Sigma – Aldrich, FOT Bulgaria The method of thiobarbituric acid (TBA), which measures MDA-reactive products, was used (Plaser et al. 1966). In brief, 1 ml plasma, 1 ml physiological solution, and 1 ml 25% trichloroacetic acid were mixed and centrifuged at 7,000 rpm for 20 min. Two milliliters protein-free supernatant was mixed with 0.5 ml 1% TBA and heated at 95°C for 1 h. After cooling, the intensity of pink color of the end fraction product was determined at 532 nm. The MDA concentration was calculated according to the following formula: where OD 532 is the optic density in $\lambda=532$ nm and extinction $1.56 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. To study the levels of antioxidant enzymes – superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalyse (CAT) we used ELISA kits (Abcam, UK) and worked according to the protocol accompanying the product. Protein carbonile content (PCC) was also measured with an ELISA kit (Sensitivity: 0.015 μM ; Abcam, UK). We received a permission to use animals in a clinical study with the № 280, issued on the basis of Art. 155, para. 7 of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the opinion of the Ethics Committee № 196 of 10.09.2020 permission from Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (BFSA) for aviary bred game birds. The data was processed with IBM SPSS Statistics (SPSS-Inc., 2019, SPSS Reference Guide 26 SPSS, Chicago, USA) and we used descriptive statistics with graphics for frequency distribution. All values were expressed as average \pm standard deviation (SD) with statistical significance of $P \leq 0.001$.

Results

The pheasants from the positive control group had very high levels of MDA (5.16 ± 0.39) and PCC (7.70 ± 0.45) (Fig. 1 and 2) compared to the levels of MDA (2.35 ± 0.19) and PCC (1.46 ± 0.25) in the negative control group ($p < 0.001$). After administration of tryptophan, the levels of MDA 3.99 ± 0.32 and PCC 3.86 ± 0.33 had a significant drop ($p < 0.001$). The effect of administering silymarin was more significant for decreasing the values of MDA (1.78 ± 0.22) and PCC (1.20 ± 0.17).

Figure 1: Changes in MDA values (mean±SD) in Black-necked pheasants (n=12) – negative control (I group); treated with 21 g/kg tryptophan (II group); treated with 10 g/kg silymarin (III group); positive control (IV group); P<0.001: 1 – vs I group; 2 – vs II group; 3 – vs III group; 4 – vs IV group.

Figure 2: Changes in PCC values (mean±SD) in Black-necked pheasants (n=12) – negative control (I group); treated with 21 g/kg tryptophan (II group); treated with 10 g/kg silymarin (III group); positive control (IV group); P<0.001: 1 – vs I group; 2 – vs II group; 3 – vs III group; 4 – vs IV group.

The tendency in SOD (Fig. 3) was the opposite as its activity in the negative control was very high (2.99 ± 0.10) while in the positive control it decreased (1.64 ± 0.20). The compensatory activity of CAT (Fig. 4) in the negative control (1.33 ± 0.24) was higher than in the positive control (6.65 ± 0.73). Silymarin had a very strong antioxidative effect alongside an increase in the activity of

SOD (3.05 ± 0.07) and a lowering of the activity of CAT (1.09 ± 0.20). The effect of administering the tryptophan was milder on the regulation of SOD activities (2.27 ± 0.21) and CAT (3.75 ± 0.32).

Figure 3: Change in the activity of SOD (mean±SD) in Black-necked pheasants (n=12) – negative control (I group); treated with 21 g/kg tryptophan (II group); treated with 10 g/kg silymarin (III group); positive control (IV group): P<0.001: 1 – vs I group; 2 – vs II group; 3 – vs III group; 4 – vs IV group.

Figure 4: Change in the activity of CAT (mean±SD) in Black-necked pheasants (n=12) – negative control (I group); treated with 21 g/kg tryptophan (II group); treated with 10 g/kg silymarin (III group); positive control (IV group): P<0.001: 1 – vs I group; 2 – vs II group; 3 - vs III group; 4 – vs IV group.

Discussion

The levels of lipid peroxidation are expressed in the accumulation of MDA which can be caused by different influencing factors (de Zwart *et al.*, 1999; Altan *et al.*, 2003). In cannibalism, the main factor according to us would be traumatism – disruption of the intactness of the tissues leading to disturbances in the metabolic processes and disturbed thermoregulation as a result of deterioration in the feathering. The oxidative disability of the proteins is determined by the accumulation of protein carbonyl groups in the organism (Dalle-Donne *et al.*, 2003). The levels of MDA and PCC in pheasant with signs of cannibalism were markedly increased than the ones determined in the clinically healthy birds. When there are high concentrations of free radicals's destructive processes can be observed in the plasma and cellular lipids and proteins which leads to a high increase in MDA and PCC in the organism of birds (Delles *et al.*, 2014; Nkuwana *et al.*, 2014).

The antioxidative system in birds eliminating the produced free radicals is due to the enzyme activities of SOD and CAT. A number of scientists determined big changes in the activity of antioxidative enzymes (SOD and CAT) in conditions of stress and different pathological processes (Zelko *et al.*, 2002; Pappasetal., 2011; Shi-Wen Xu *et al.*, 2013) due to high lipid peroxidation causing oxidative stress in the organism of birds (Koinarski *et al.*, 2006; Стоянчев, 2019) including the cannibalism found in our studies of pheasants. The activity of SOD in pheasants with signs of cannibalism is markedly low due to the expressed oxidative stress. The catalase activity got compensatively high in order to limit the lowering of SOD activity. Some authors prove that in birds exposed to temperature stress SOD and CAT activity changes (Altan *et al.*, 2003; Yamazaki *et al.*, 2003; Vladimirov, 2004), and in our studies that would be due to the stress caused by injurious pecking.

The treatment of cannibalistic pheasants with tryptophan significantly lowers the lipid peroxidation and the oxidation of the proteins which leads to a decrease in the levels of MDA ad PCC in the organisms of the experimental individuals. In a similar way, the activity of the antioxidative enzymes (SOD and CAT) is regulated – an increase in SOD and compensatory lowering of CAT. The lack of proteins in the forage of homebred birds significantly increases oxidative stress (Popova and Popov, 2002; Stoyanchev, 2019). Adding more protein (21 g/kg tryptophan) in the main forage pheasants better their protein metabolism which reflects on the improvement of their studied values.

The protective effect of *Silybum marianum* and its standardized extract of seeds is due to the lowering of the protein and lipid peroxidation (MDA and PCC) and increase in the produced antioxidants that keep the integrity of the plasma and organoid membranes and proteins which prevents the destruction of cells in the organism (Upadhyay *et al.*, 2010; Karimi *et al.*, 2011; Stoev *et al.*, 2021). Pheasants with an intake of 10 g/kg silymarin in the forage have a significant improvement of all studied values for oxidative stress (MDA and PCC) and antioxidative enzymes (SOD and CAT).

Conclusion

In black-necked pheasants with signs of cannibalism there are very high levels of lipid and protein peroxidation (MDA and PCC); lowered activity of antioxidative enzyme SOD and a compensatory increase in CAT. All of that leads to highly expressed oxidative stress in pheasants with signs of cannibalism.

The administration of 10 g/kg silymarin in the forage of cannibalistic pheasants significantly and strongly lowers the production of MDA and PCC; increases the activity of the antioxidative

enzyme SOD and compensatively lowers the activity of CAT. Silymarin has a very strong antioxidative effect and is recommended as a supplement for improvement in the condition of pheasants exhibiting signs of cannibalism.

The administration of 21 g/kg tryptophan in the forage of cannibalistic pheasants moderately decreases MDA and PCC; increases the activity of antioxidative enzyme SOD and compensatively lowers CAT. Tryptophan has positive effects and improves the conditions of pheasants with cannibalism damage.

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